

Does Adoption of an Affirmative Action Policy Constitute an Act Discreditable to the Profession? A Philosophical Look at a Practical Ethical Question

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Abstract

Rule 501 of the AICPA's Code of Professional Conduct prohibits acts that are discreditable to the profession, as do the codes of ethics of several other professional accounting organizations. The AICPA Code includes employment discrimination as an act discreditable to the profession. Many firms have adopted affirmative action programs in an attempt to prevent discrimination. The problem is that affirmative action programs favor certain groups over others on the basis of race or gender, thus making them discriminatory programs. The author questions whether the adoption of an affirmative action policy constitutes an act discreditable to the profession, since affirmative action programs are discriminatory and since discriminatory employment practices constitute acts discreditable to the profession.

Rule 501 of the AICPA's Code of Professional Conduct prohibits acts that are discreditable to the profession. The rule states: "A member shall not commit an act discreditable to the

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profession.”² AICPA members can be reprimanded or even expelled from membership for violating this provision. But potential punishment is not limited to AICPA members. Nonmembers may also be bound by the AICPA’s Code of Professional Conduct.³

The AICPA is not the only professional accounting organization that prohibits acts discreditable to the profession. The Code of Ethics of the Institute of Internal Auditors states: “Members and CIAs shall not knowingly engage in acts or activities which are discreditable to the profession of internal auditing or to their organization.”⁴

The Code of Ethics of the Association of Government Accountants also prohibits discreditable acts. In the personal behavior section it states: “A member shall not engage in acts or be associated with activities which are contrary to the public interest or bring discredit to the Association of Government Accountants.”⁵

The old (1988) version of Interpretation 501-2 of the AICPA’s Rule 501 stated:

Discrimination in employment practices.
Discrimination based on race, color, religion, sex,
age or national origin in hiring, promotion or salary
practices is presumed to constitute an act

² Rule 501, reprinted in MARY BETH ARMSTRONG, *ETHICS AND PROFESSIONALISM FOR CPAS* (Cincinnati: South-Western Publishing Co., 1993), 66. This version was adopted January 12, 1988. Also available at <http://www.aicpa.org/about/code/et501.htm>.

³ Courts have used AICPA rules to determine minimum levels of performance. See DENZIL Y. CAUSEY, JR., AND SANDRA A. CAUSEY, *DUTIES AND LIABILITIES OF PUBLIC ACCOUNTANTS*, fifth edition (1995), at 19, 29, 77; Stanley L. Bloch, *Inc. v. Klein*, 258 N.Y.S.2d 501 (N.Y. Sup. Ct. 1965).

⁴ Code of Ethics, Institute of Internal Auditors (1988), *Standards of Conduct III*, reprinted in ARMSTRONG, *supra*, at 125.

⁵ Bylaws, ART. I, Sec. 3, reprinted in ARMSTRONG, *supra*, at 127.

discreditable to the profession in violation of Rule 501.⁶

The revised Interpretation states:

Discrimination and harassment in employment practices. Whenever a member is finally determined by a court of competent jurisdiction to have violated any of the antidiscrimination laws of the United States or any state or municipality thereof, including those related to sexual and other forms of harassment, or has waived or lost his/her right of appeal after a hearing by an administrative agency, the member will be presumed to have committed an act discreditable to the profession in violation of rule 501.⁷

According to this Interpretation, discrimination is presumed to constitute an act discreditable to the profession. The big question is what is discrimination? This term is not defined, perhaps because there is no need to define it. Everyone knows what discrimination is. Or do they?

Discrimination means that we do not treat individuals equally. We prefer some individuals over others or we treat some individuals as less equal than others. If a firm refuses to hire blacks because of their race, they are discriminating against blacks. But what if a firm makes a policy decision to hire at least two blacks this year? That policy is called affirmative action.⁸

⁶ Reprinted in ARMSTRONG, *supra*, at 67.

⁷ Revised effective November 30, 1997 by the Professional Ethics Executive Committee of the AICPA. <http://www.aicpa.org/about/code/et501.htm>.

⁸ For a discussion of affirmative action policies applied to accounting firms, see Roger Clegg, *Accounting for Preferences*, 1 JOURNAL OF ACCOUNTING, ETHICS & PUBLIC POLICY (Spring 1998).

How does affirmative action differ from discrimination? Affirmative action has as one objective the overcoming of past discrimination. It is based on a non sequitur. If the great grandparents of a 25 year-old black who is now applying for employment were discriminated against, then we have to make up for that by discriminating against non-blacks who might have applied for the same job. One injustice was perpetrated against the current black applicant's great grandparents. Now, a second injustice is being perpetrated against the great grand child of some white people who might or might not have been responsible for the discrimination that was perpetrated against the great grandparents of the black applicant. The whole affirmative action argument is illogical and convoluted.

Affirmative action is rightly called reverse discrimination. Rather than discrimination against some minority, it is discrimination against the majority. But even this statement is not completely accurate. Women are considered a proper category for affirmative action. Yet women comprise more than 50 percent of the population. Thus, in the case of women, who are given preferential treatment because of affirmative action, it can also be a policy that discriminates in favor of the majority or against a minority (men).

But the question is not one of discriminating in favor of some minority or majority but whether there is discrimination in the first place. By definition, discrimination exists if some employer favors some individuals over others. That is the case even if the favoritism is based on merit, which is perhaps the best kind of discrimination. If it were possible to identify which individuals would be best qualified for the job, it would make sense to hire them rather than others who are less well qualified. That is a legitimate form of discrimination. We cannot say that all discrimination is bad. Some forms of discrimination – like choosing on the basis of merit – are good.

Rule 501 presumes that employment discrimination based on race, color, religion, sex, age or national origin constitute an act discreditable to the profession. Since affirmative action policies

are discriminatory on these very bases, we can conclude that a firm that adopts an affirmative action policy is committing an act discreditable to the profession.